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THE SHANNON ENTROPY OF FIBONACCI NUMBERS

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ABSTRACT

Entropy is used as a tool to evaluate uncertainty of systems in the information sciences. Fibonacci number sequence is often appeared in the nature which is very related to golden ratio. Moreover, an early study shows that Fibonacci number sequence has maximum entropy in terms of thermodynamics in the nature. In this paper we compute the Shannon entropy of Fibonacci number sequence by the sum of these numbers. We obtain that the entropy measure is approached to 2.51179. In order to make some extra observations, we compute the Shannon entropy measures of odd indexed, even indexed Fibonacci numbers and the squares of Fibonacci numbers via the sum of these sequences. We obtain a very interesting result that the Shannon entropies of the mentioned sequences are approached to same value 1.55237.

1. INTRODUCTION

Although the entropy is known a physical topic, after the seminal study “A mathematical theory of communication” of Claude Shannon [7], it has been widely used

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in the information sciences. Fibonacci number sequence is often appeared in the nature. It represents the increasing problem of rabbits. Moreover, the ratio of two consecutive Fibonacci numbers is approached to golden ratio. More details about Fibonacci numbers can be found in the book Koshy[4].

The number of studies about the entropy of Fibonacci number is limited. The Shannon entropy of Fibonacci trees which are the graph theoretic representations of Fibonacci numbers was obtained by Horibe in 1981 Horibe[2]. Takashi Aurues observed the thermodynamic properties of Fibonacci numbers in 2013 Aurues[1] and he obtained that Fibonacci number sequence has thermodynamic maximum entropy in the nature. Haruo Hosoya showed that Fibonacci number sequence is very related the maximum entropy measures of molecular surface electrons Hosoya[3]. The entropy measure two step Fibonacci words was obtained by Nilsson in 2013 Nilsson[6].

Another application of entropy to number theory can be found for prime numbers. Since there is no a general recurrence relation to find all prime numbers, entropy measures of some prime number sequences were studied by Lacasa et al. Lacasa[5]. They used prime number theorem for computing the average number of primes.

In this paper, we compute the Shannon entropy of Fibonacci number sequence. We obtain the probably distributions by the sum of Fibonacci numbers. We obtain that the entropy measure is approached to 2.51179. Moreover, we obtain that the Shannon entropy measure of odd indexed, even indexed Fibonacci numbers and the squares of Fibonacci numbers are approached to same value 1.55237.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 1. *Fibonacci number sequence is obtained by the recurrence relation $f_n = f_{n-1} + f_{n-2}$ for $n \geq 3$ with initial terms $f_1 = f_2 = 1$ Koshy[4].*

The first eight Fibonacci numbers are $f_1 = 1, f_2 = 1, f_3 = 2, f_4 = 3, f_5 = 5, f_6 = 8, f_7 = 13, f_8 = 21$. The graph in the Figure 1 shows how the Fibonacci numbers stack up.

The ratio of consecutive Fibonacci numbers $\frac{f_{n+1}}{f_n}$ for the first 15 Fibonacci numbers is listed below Koshy[4].

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{f_2}{f_1} &= \frac{1}{1} = 1.0000000000, & \frac{f_3}{f_2} &= \frac{2}{1} = 2.0000000000, & \frac{f_4}{f_3} &= \frac{3}{2} = 1.5000000000, \\ \frac{f_5}{f_4} &= \frac{5}{3} \approx 1.6666666667, & \frac{f_6}{f_5} &= \frac{8}{5} \approx 1.6000000000, & \frac{f_7}{f_6} &= \frac{13}{8} \approx 1.6250000000, \\ \frac{f_8}{f_7} &= \frac{21}{13} \approx 1.6153846154, & \frac{f_9}{f_8} &= \frac{34}{21} \approx 1.6190476191, & \frac{f_{10}}{f_9} &= \frac{55}{34} \approx 1.6176470588, \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1: Fibonacci numbers.

$$\frac{f_{11}}{f_{10}} = \frac{89}{55} \approx 1.6181818182, \quad \frac{f_{12}}{f_{11}} = \frac{144}{89} \approx 1.6179775281, \quad \frac{f_{13}}{f_{12}} = \frac{233}{144} \approx 1.6180555556,$$

$$\frac{f_{14}}{f_{13}} = \frac{377}{233} \approx 1.6180257511, \quad \frac{f_{15}}{f_{14}} = \frac{610}{377} \approx 1.6180371353.$$

If n is taken very large, the ratio $\frac{f_{n+1}}{f_n}$ approaches a limit $1.618033\dots$ which is called golden ratio Koshy[4].

Haruo Hosoya found an important result in 1971 about Fibonacci numbers Hosoya[3]. In graph theory, a path graph P_n consists of n consecutive vertices and $n - 1$ edges. If a subset of the edges has the property that no two edges share a common vertex, it is called a matching. Total number of matchings of a path P_n equals to Fibonacci number f_{n+1} . Total number of matchings is called Hosoya index or Z-index in graph theory. It means that $Z(P_n) = f_{n+1}$.

For example, the path graph $P_6 : v_1v_2v_3v_4v_5v_6$ is depicted in Figure 2. We can show the matchings as follows. The empty set is accepted a matching oneself. The each one of one edge sets $\{v_1v_2\}$, $\{v_2v_3\}$, $\{v_3v_4\}$, $\{v_4v_5\}$, $\{v_5v_6\}$ is a matching. Moreover, the matchings of P_6 which have two elements are $\{v_1v_2, v_3v_4\}$,

Figure 2: The path graph P_6 .

$\{v_1v_2, v_4v_5\}$, $\{v_1v_2, v_5v_6\}$, $\{v_2v_3, v_4v_5\}$, $\{v_2v_3, v_5v_6\}$, $\{v_3v_4, v_5v_6\}$. The matching contains three elements is $\{v_1v_2, v_3v_4, v_5v_6\}$.

If we denote a matching of k elements by $Z(P_6, k)$, it is obtained that $Z(P_6, 0) = 1$, $Z(P_6, 1) = 5$, $Z(P_6, 2) = 6$ and $Z(P_6, 3) = 1$. It implies that

$$Z(P_6) = \sum_{k=0}^3 Z(P_6, k) = 13 = f_7.$$

The Hosoya index was applied to chemical molecules and it is obtained that some physico-chemical properties of these molecules have good correlations with Hosoya index Hosoya[3].

Definition 2. For a given probably distribution $p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n$ such that $0 \leq p_i \leq 1$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 1$, the Shannon's entropy I is presented by the following equation Shannon[7]

$$I = - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2 p_i.$$

In order to simplify the writing, we use $\log p_i$ instead of $\log_2 p_i$.

Theorem 3. The sums of the Fibonacci numbers, even indexed Fibonacci numbers, odd indexed Fibonacci numbers and the squares of Fibonacci numbers are obtained by the following equations Koshy[4]

- i) $\sum_{i=1}^n f_i = f_1 + f_2 + \dots + f_n = f_{n+2} - 1$
- ii) $\sum_{i=1}^n f_{2i} = f_2 + f_4 + \dots + f_{2n} = f_{2n+1} - 1$
- iii) $\sum_{i=1}^n f_{2i-1} = f_1 + f_3 + \dots + f_{2n-1} = f_{2n}$
- iv) $\sum_{i=1}^n f_i^2 = f_1^2 + f_2^2 + \dots + f_n^2 = f_n f_{n+1}$.

3. MAIN RESULTS

We can define the Shannon entropy measures of the Fibonacci numbers, even indexed Fibonacci numbers, odd indexed Fibonacci numbers and the squares of Fibonacci numbers by Definition 2 and Theorem 3 as in the following definition. We obtain the probably distributions via the sum of Fibonacci numbers.

Definition 4.

i) The Shannon entropy measure of the Fibonacci numbers is obtained by the following equation

$$\begin{aligned} I_F &= - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i} \log \frac{f_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i} \\ &= - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_i}{f_{n+2} - 1} \log \frac{f_i}{f_{n+2} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

ii) The Shannon entropy measure of the even indexed Fibonacci numbers is obtained by the following equation

$$\begin{aligned} I_F &= - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_{2i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_{2i}} \log \frac{f_{2i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_{2i}} \\ &= - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_{2i}}{f_{2n+1} - 1} \log \frac{f_{2i}}{f_{2n+1} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

iii) The Shannon entropy measure of the odd indexed Fibonacci numbers is obtained by the following equation

$$\begin{aligned} I_F &= - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_{2i-1}}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_{2i-1}} \log \frac{f_{2i-1}}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_{2i-1}} \\ &= - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_{2i-1}}{f_{2n}} \log \frac{f_{2i-1}}{f_{2n}}. \end{aligned}$$

iv) The Shannon entropy measure of the squares of Fibonacci numbers is obtained by the following equation

$$\begin{aligned} I_F &= - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i^2} \log \frac{f_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i^2} \\ &= - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_i^2}{f_n f_{n+1}} \log \frac{f_i^2}{f_n f_{n+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

Example 5. The first four Fibonacci numbers are $f_1 = 1$, $f_2 = 1$, $f_3 = 2$, $f_4 = 3$. Then, we can calculate the I_F by

$$I_F = -\frac{1}{7} \log \frac{1}{7} - \frac{1}{7} \log \frac{1}{7} - \frac{2}{7} \log \frac{2}{7} - \frac{3}{7} \log \frac{3}{7} = 1.84237.$$

If we do these calculations all Fibonacci numbers, we use the algorithm below and we get the graph in Figure 4.

Algorithm 1: Pseudocode for the Shannon entropy measures of Fibonacci numbers

```

fibonacci(n){
  if (n <= 2) return 1
  else return fibonacci(n-1) + fibonacci(n-2)}
for k to range_n
  for j to k+1
    f_entropy[j]=-(fibonacci(j)/(fibonacci(k+2)-1)*
    log2(fibonacci(j)/(fibonacci(k+2)-1)
  for t to k+1
    s +=f_entropy[t]
    sum[t]=s
  entropy_sum[k]=sum[k]
print(entropy_sum)

```

Example 6. The first four even indexed Fibonacci numbers are $f_2 = 1$, $f_4 = 3$, $f_6 = 8$, $f_8 = 21$. Then, we obtain that $f_2 + f_4 + f_6 + f_8 = 33 = f_9 - 1$. So, we can calculate the I_F by

$$I_F = -\frac{1}{33} \log \frac{1}{33} - \frac{3}{33} \log \frac{3}{33} - \frac{8}{33} \log \frac{8}{33} - \frac{21}{33} \log \frac{21}{33} = 1.37792.$$

If we do these calculations all even indexed Fibonacci numbers, we use the algorithm below and we get the graph in Figure 3.

Algorithm 2: Pseudocode for the Shannon entropy measures of even indexed Fibonacci numbers

```

fibonacci(n){
  if (n <= 2) return 1
  else return fibonacci(n-1) + fibonacci(n-2)}
for k to range_n
  for j=1 to k+1
    f_entropy[j]=-(fibonacci(2j)/(fibonacci(2k+1)-1)*
    log2(fibonacci(2j)/(fibonacci(2k+1)-1)
  for t=1 to k+1
    s +=f_entropy[t]
    sum[t]=s
  entropy_sum[k]=sum[k]
print(entropy_sum)

```

Example 7. The first four odd indexed Fibonacci numbers are $f_1 = 1$, $f_3 = 2$, $f_5 = 5$, $f_7 = 13$. Then, we obtain that $f_1 + f_3 + f_5 + f_7 = 21 = f_8$. So, we can calculate the I_F by

$$I_F = -\frac{1}{21} \log \frac{1}{21} - \frac{2}{21} \log \frac{2}{21} - \frac{5}{21} \log \frac{5}{21} - \frac{13}{21} \log \frac{13}{21} = 1.45349.$$

Figure 3: The graphs for even-odd and square entropy.

If we do these calculations all odd indexed Fibonacci numbers, we use the algorithm below and we get the graph in Figure 3.

Algorithm 3: Pseudocode for the Shannon entropy measures of odd indexed Fibonacci numbers

```

fibonacci(n){
  if (n <= 2) return 1
  else return fibonacci(n-1) + fibonacci(n-2)}
for k to range_n
  for j=1 to k+1
    f_entropy[j]=-(fibonacci(2j-1)/fibonacci(2k))*
    log2(fibonacci(2j-1)/fibonacci(2k))
  for t=1 to k+1
    s +=f_entropy[t]
  sum[t]=s
  entropy_sum[k]=sum[k]
print(entropy_sum)

```

Example 8. The squares of the first four Fibonacci numbers are $f_1^2 = 1$, $f_2^2 = 1$, $f_3^2 = 4$, $f_4^2 = 9$. Then, we obtain that $f_1^2 + f_2^2 + f_3^2 + f_4^2 = 15 = f_4 f_5$. So, we can

calculate the I_F by

$$I_F = -\frac{1}{15} \log \frac{1}{15} - \frac{1}{15} \log \frac{1}{15} - \frac{4}{15} \log \frac{4}{15} - \frac{9}{15} \log \frac{9}{15} = 1.4716.$$

If we do these calculations the squares of Fibonacci numbers, we use the algorithm below and we get the graph in Figure 3. We can also see the graphs of all entropy types in Figure 4 comparative form.

Algorithm 4: Pseudocode for the Shannon entropy measures of the squares of Fibonacci numbers

```

fibonacci(n){
  if (n <= 2) return 1
  else return fibonacci(n-1) + fibonacci(n-2)}
for k to range_n
  for j=1 to k+1
    f_entropy[j]=-(fibonacci(j) fibonacci(j))/(fibonacci(k) fibonacci(k+1))*
    log2(fibonacci(j) fibonacci(j))/(fibonacci(k) fibonacci(k+1))
  for t=1 to k+1
    s +=f_entropy[t]
  sum[t]=s
  entropy_sum[k]=sum[k]
print(entropy_sum)

```

The Shannon entropy measures of the first 35 terms of Fibonacci numbers, odd indexed Fibonacci numbers, even indexed Fibonacci numbers and squares of Fibonacci numbers presented in Table 1. We can see that the entropy measure of Fibonacci numbers reached its maximum value 2.51179 with the term f_{32} . Moreover, the entropy measure reached its maximum value 1.55237 for squares of Fibonacci numbers with f_{14} , for odd indexed Fibonacci numbers with f_{27} and for even indexed Fibonacci numbers with f_{32} .

It is understood that the squares of Fibonacci numbers are quickly increased and the entropy measure has reached its maximum value earlier than other three sequences. Since odd indexed and even indexed Fibonacci numbers are increased with two terms, they are quickly increased from the Fibonacci numbers. Then, the entropy of subsequences (odd and even indexed) Fibonacci numbers reached their maximum values earlier than the Fibonacci sequence.

The most interesting result of the paper is the equality of the entropies of squares of Fibonacci numbers and the odd-even indexed Fibonacci numbers. In normal conditions, the squares of a group numbers are changed more than these number. It is expected that the entropy of the squares of these numbers is bigger than the entropy of these numbers. But here, the entropy of squares of the Fibonacci numbers equals the entropy of two subsequences of Fibonacci numbers which is smaller than the entropy of the Fibonacci numbers.

Figure 4: The graphs for all entropy types.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we applied the Shannon entropy to Fibonacci number sequence. We obtain the entropy measures for Fibonacci numbers, odd and even indexed Fibonacci numbers and squares of Fibonacci numbers. We made a concrete study between the number theory and information sciences. This study gives a measure the uncertainty of Fibonacci number sequence.

There are many other entropy measures in the literature. Therefore, the similar investigations can be made for these entropy measures.

Bibliography

1. T. Aurues. The Fibonacci sequence in nature implies thermodynamic maximum entropy. *Kokyuroku of Res. Inst. Math. Sci. Kyoto Univ.*, 1852 (2013), 165-176.
2. T. Horibe. An entropy view of Fibonacci trees. *The Fibonacci Quarterly*, 20 (1982), 168-178.
3. H. Hosoya. Topological index. A newly proposed quantity characterizing the topological nature of structural isomers of saturated hydrocarbons. *Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Japan*, 44 (1971), 2332-2339.
4. T. Koshy. *Fibonacci and Lucas Numbers with Applications*. New York, USA: Wiley, 2001.

5. L. Lacasa, B. Luque, I. Gomes, I. Miramontes. On a dynamical approach to some prime number sequences. *Entropy*, 20 (2018), 131. doi: 10.3390/e20020131.
6. J. Nilsson. On the entropy of a two step random Fibonacci substitutions. *Entropy*, 15 (2013), 3312-3324. doi: 10.3390/e15093312
7. C. Shannon. A Mathematical theory of communication. *The Bell System Technical Journal*, 27 (1948), 379-423, 623-656.

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Table 1: The Shannon entropy of Fibonacci numbers, odd indexed-even indexed Fibonacci numbers and squares of Fibonacci numbers.

Fibonacci(n)	n	normal_entropy(n)	odd_entropy(n)	even_entropy(n)	square_entropy(n)
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
1	2	1	0.918296	0.811278	1
2	3	1.5	1.29879	1.18872	1.25163
3	4	1.84237	1.45349	1.37792	1.4716
5	5	2.05459	1.51429	1.47116	1.50628
8	6	2.2037	1.53778	1.51558	1.54058
13	7	2.30287	1.54679	1.53607	1.5456
21	8	2.37139	1.55024	1.54528	1.55065
34	9	2.41758	1.55156	1.54933	1.55138
55	10	2.44898	1.55206	1.55108	1.55212
89	11	2.47006	1.55225	1.55183	1.55223
144	12	2.4842	1.55233	1.55215	1.55234
233	13	2.49361	1.55235	1.55228	1.55235
377	14	2.49986	1.55237	1.55233	1.55237
610	15	2.50398	1.55237	1.55236	1.55237
987	16	2.5067	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
1597	17	2.50848	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
2584	18	2.50964	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
4181	19	2.5104	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
6765	20	2.51089	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
10946	21	2.51121	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
17711	22	2.51142	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
28657	23	2.51155	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
46368	24	2.51164	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
75025	25	2.51169	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
121393	26	2.51173	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
196418	27	2.51175	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
317811	28	2.51177	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
514229	29	2.51177	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
832040	30	2.51178	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
1346269	31	2.51178	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
2178309	32	2.51179	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
3524578	33	2.51179	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
5702887	34	2.51179	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237
9227465	35	2.51179	1.55237	1.55237	1.55237